

Onsager's Relations in Membrane Transport Processes

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It is only recently that thermodynamic theory of irreversible processes¹ based on Onsager's relations and linear phenomenological laws has been applied by Kedem and Katchalsky² to the phenomena of membrane transport in biology. This approach has not only led to a generalised theory of transport processes through membranes but has also disclosed errors in the past methods³. But more recently Bresler and Wendt⁴ have questioned the validity of Onsager's theorem in the non-equilibrium thermodynamic theory of transport processes through membranes as developed by Kedem and Katchalsky². Since the article of Bresler and Wendt raises an issue of fundamental importance, we have examined the arguments contained in their paper and found their analysis to be inconsistent. This is what has been reported in the present communication. Since the theory of Kedem and Katchalsky forms the basis of the arguments of Bresler and Wendt, we summarise it below for the sake of completeness and readability of the note.

Consider an isothermal system comprising two compartments I and II containing binary solution of different concentrations of a non-electrolyte and separated by an open membrane. The solutions in both the compartments are dilute in solute and are well stirred. For such a system the dissipation function ϕ is given by²

$$\phi = J_v \Delta P + J_D \Delta \pi \quad \dots (1)$$

Where J_v is the solution flux and is loosely referred to as water flux. J_D , the exchange flow is the relative velocity of solute with respect to that of water. ΔP and $\Delta \pi$ are the differences in hydrostatic pressure and osmotic pressure across the membrane respectively. J_v and J_D are related to the solute flux J_s and the water flux J_w in the following manner

$$J_v = J_w \bar{V}_w + J_s \bar{V}_s \quad \dots (2)$$

$$J_D = \frac{J_s}{\bar{C}_s} - J_w \bar{V}_w \quad \dots (3)$$

where \bar{V}_w and \bar{V}_s are the partial molar volumes of water and solute respectively. \bar{C}_s represents the numerical average of the concentrations on the two sides of the membrane

i.e. $\bar{C}_s = \frac{C_s^I + C_s^{II}}{2}$ provided $(C_s^I - C_s^{II})$ is small. In view of equation (1) the linear

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phenomenological relations between fluxes and forces can be written as

$$J_v = L_{PP} \Delta P + L_{PD} \Delta \pi \quad \dots (4)$$

$$J_D = L_{DP} \Delta P + L_{DD} \Delta \pi \quad \dots (5)$$

where L_{PP} is the hydraulic conductivity and L_{DD} represents the diffusional mobility per unit osmotic pressure at $\Delta P = 0$. L_{PD} and L_{DP} are the cross phenomenological coefficients which according to Onsager's theorem should be equal to each other.

Bresler and Wendt in their paper⁴ do not object to equation (1). They only offer a different interpretation of J_D . According to them a true diffusive flow must vanish for sufficiently rapid bulk flow⁵. Since according to equation (1) J_D cannot vanish for any value of bulk flow whatsoever, Bresler and Wendt argue that J_D cannot be identified with a true diffusive flow. Bresler and Wendt in their paper have attempted to prove that in the non-equilibrium thermodynamic treatment of membrane transport by Kedem and Katchalsky, the coefficient L_{PD} is equal to zero while the coefficient L_{DP} is nonzero and thus concluded that Onsager's theorem is not valid. For proving $L_{PD} = 0$ they consider the bulk flow processes from one well stirred compartment to another, the concentrations of the solutions in the two compartments being unequal. For such a process they say that concentration difference will have no effect on J_v , hence L_{PD} which measures the effect of $\Delta \pi$ on J_v , must be equal to zero for an open membrane. For proving $L_{DP} \neq 0$ they advance another set of arguments. They say that J_D must increase as J_v increases, because the production of entropy due to mixing must increase the faster the solutions are mixed. This will make J_D depend on J_v which according to them depends on ΔP only and therefore J_D must also depend on ΔP . On the basis of the argument advanced above they conclude that L_{DP} in equation (5) must not be equal to zero.

The quantitative analysis of their arguments starts with the equation

$$J_s = C_s^I J_v \quad \dots (6)$$

where C_s^I is the concentration of the solution in the compartment I. With the help of equations (2), (3), (4), and (6) they obtain the following expression for J_D

$$J_D = L_{PP} \left(\frac{C_s^I}{\bar{C}_s} - 1 \right) \Delta P + L_{PD} \left(\frac{C_s^I}{\bar{C}_s} - 1 \right) \Delta \pi \quad \dots (7)$$

using the approximation $C_s^I \bar{V}_s \ll 1$ for dilute solutions. Comparing equation (7) with equation (5) they write

$$L_{DP} = L_{PP} \left(\frac{C_s^I}{\bar{C}_s} - 1 \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

From equation (8) they conclude that L_{DP} will not be equal to zero unless

$$C_s^I = C_s^{II} = \bar{C}_s \quad \dots (9)$$

which by no means represents the general situation.

Here we would like to draw attention to the fact that in equation (6) the condition (9) has already been assumed in addition to $J_D = 0$. This can be easily demonstrated. From equations (2) and (3) we can write

$$J_v + J_D = \frac{J_s}{\bar{C}_s} (\bar{C}_s \bar{V}_s + 1) \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

which for dilute solutions where $\bar{C}_s \bar{V}_s \ll 1$ can be transformed into $J_s = C_s^I J_v$ only if $J_D = 0$ and the condition (9) is obeyed. Therefore if equation (6) is taken to be valid L_{DP} has to be equal to zero on account of condition (9) which is implied in equation (6). This as a matter of fact proves the validity of Onsager's theorem rather than disproving it.

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